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The Impact of Anglicisms on Ukrainian Undergraduates as Consumers of Social Media Content

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Abstract

This study investigates the use of English as a non-native language in communication and media consumption on social networks. It further examines the interaction between native and foreign languages within the linguistic environment of a Ukrainian academic institution. Additionally, it explores perceptions of English in media content creation and its role in modern marketing and public relations strategies employed by the institution through social networks. Based on descriptive analysis, using Google Analytics tools, of a survey of 385 Ukrainian university matriculated and prospective students, the study reveals a high diffusion rate of English as a foreign language and a relatively high level of proficiency, averaging between B1 and B2 (on the CEFR Global Scale) among 75% of the target audiences, which creates favourable conditions for English use in the processes of communication and creation of media content for the Ukrainian higher education institution. These results reveal the effectiveness of integrating the study of English as a non-native language into personal communications, media content creation, and communications of higher education institutions with students and applicants via social networks. The study suggests that higher education institutions should leverage the high level of English proficiency among students to enhance academic and media communication strategies. Furthermore, aligning institutional content with students' linguistic practices can strengthen engagement and improve overall communication effectiveness.

Keywords: English language, language environment, student context, social network communication, media content, higher education institutions

1 Introduction

In modern societies, communication is crucial for advancing fundamental processes, particularly in economics, marketing, and social interactions. The rapid advancement of digital technologies has significantly impacted the volume, forms, and speed of information consumption and the nature of media content.

The COVID-19 pandemic has intensified these processes, significantly increasing the engagement of all stakeholders in the communication ecosystem: content creators, consumers, and distributors (including channels and platforms that facilitate the distribution of media content, such as websites and social networks). As a result,

the significance of language and social networks in shaping the media environment and constructing effective communication during crises – such as the COVID-19 pandemic from 2020 to 2022 and the conflict in Ukraine in 2022 – has increased substantially.

Within the context of social networks, an individual can simultaneously act both as a generator and a consumer of media content. Communication can be established in both one-on-one interactions and group settings, such as social network groups. Communication channels, including internet platforms such as Facebook, Messenger, Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp, Google+, Instagram, and blogs, significantly determine or influence the form and style of content. YouTube and TikTok, in particular, provide video formats with specific technical specifications for media content. In contrast, platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Pinterest are oriented toward graphic content. Additionally, various messaging applications like Telegram and WhatsApp facilitate the combination of diverse forms of content, serving as supplementary or alternative communication channels.

2 Literature Review

The language of communication is indispensable to media content consumption and social interaction as a primary means of conveying messages. Consequently, visual content, copywriting, and their effective combinations are prioritised as practical tools in contemporary social media and marketing communications.

Media content creation plays a pivotal role both in the substance and functionality of social networks (Safari et al. 2023, Madio & Quinn 2023). As a result, numerous studies have investigated user behaviour related to content creation and information dissemination within these platforms (e.g., Jacobson & Harrison 2021).

Numerous studies have explored the behavioural characteristics and social interactions of users on social networks (Li, et al. 2013, Gil de Zúñiga et al. 2023, Seidman 2020). Additionally, extensive research has been conducted on the role of youth in content creation and communication on social media (Sirmayanti et al. 2022, Stepnik 2023). Scholars have also examined young people's perceptions of content personalisation on social networks (Claes et al. 2021), students' use of English for communication on these platforms (Thurairaj et al. 2014), and the cultural aspects of students' language use (Hussien 2018). Moreover, studies have investigated the impact of social media on the competence of international students (Alharthi 2023) and the social network usage and Internet communication practices of adolescents (Cingel et al. 2014).

Young people, who are predominantly engaged in the learning process in economically developed countries and often represent the primary audience for higher education institutions, are deeply immersed in digital technologies and social networks. As a result, the role of communication by higher education institutions on social networks has become more and more important (Fürst et al. 2021, Fürst et al. 2022, Capriotti et al. 2023, Sörensen et al. 2023).

Language serves as a fundamental means of communication both in the educational process and within social networks. This has led to analyses of language from systemic, cultural, and pragmatic perspectives. Consequently, the linguistic dimensions of media content creation and consumption are inherently interdisciplinary and extensively addressed in scientific research. Specifically, studies encompass a range of topics, including language, communications, modern digital technologies, network communications, and online communities:

- Functional aspects of language communication in social networks and content creation:
 - English language and social media content (Thurairaj et al. 2020), using different languages on social media (Esteron 2021), the association between screen media quantity, content, context and language development (Alroqi et al. 2022, Al Tamimi & Malik 2020);
 - Functional aspects of social network individual or group language communication (Adrianto & Ariesta 2022); language and behaviour in social networks (Preoțiu-Pietro et al. 2015);
 - The impact of social media on the English language (Thurairaj et al. 2014, Sharma 2017, Saeed 2021, Sultan 2023).
- Mental health, emotional, and moral aspects of language communication:
 - Emotions in social media and language as a transmission medium (Mehrotra & Chawla 2021, Wang & Lee 2020);
 - The moral aspect of language communication in social networks, specifically the identification of offensive language in Twitter media content (Seemann et al. 2023); overuse of moral language reduces engagement with social media content (Candia-Castro et al. 2022);
 - Mental health status, language use and social media behaviour patterns (Przepiorka et al. 2021).
- Applied linguistics and sociolinguistics:
 - Interdisciplinary research on the effects of applied linguistics, sociolinguistics, anthropology, technology, communication studies, and cognitive and behavioural psychology on language use (Fareen 2020);
 - The use of native and non-native English in communication and its influence and interaction with national languages (Rahmatullah, 2020, Al Tamimi & Smith 2023, Fareen 2020, Al-Rojaie 2023);
 - Semantic changes in the English language and neologisms in social networks (Jahan & Irfan 2021).
- Digital technologies and learning English:
 - Texting behaviour and language skills in children and adults (Waldron et al. 2015), text messaging effects on literacy (Verheijen 2013), grammar in text messaging (Wood et al. 2014);

- Digital technologies and social networks as a tool for learning English (Qadi 2021, Wannas & Hassan 2023, Amin et al. 2020, Abbasi 2020, Cabillon 2023, Yadav 2021, Hanim 2021, Voyce Li 2017).

Despite the wealth of research on this topic, there is a need for further investigation into the theory and practice of anglicisms and their impact on students as consumers of media content on social networks. An important task is to synthesise practical experiences related to the use and perception of anglicisms in media content and communication within social networks among non-native English-speaking students and applicants. Consequently, concepts related to media content, such as content form, presentation style, linguistic components, and communication language, are being re-evaluated. Also, despite the multitude of studies on the topic, little is still known about the impact of anglicism on Ukrainian college students as social media content consumers. This paucity constitutes a gap in the literature that the present study attempts to bridge.

The status of English as a *lingua franca* opens up new opportunities for media presence, communication, learning, business, and audience engagement. The proliferation of the English language is accelerating alongside the growth of social networking sites.

In a communication environment where English is not the native language for the majority of the audience, further research is needed on the use of English in developing communications and creating media content.

Under current conditions in education, presence in the media space and the construction of communication in English are equally important for individuals (e.g., students, teachers) and groups (e.g., student groups, university departments, and higher education institutions as a whole).

Using English in creating media content in higher education institutions and its use by the target audience, college, and prospective students, is becoming an imperative task for these institutions. Specifically, aspects of the speech profile of the target audience, such as the native language of communication and its use, foreign languages spoken by the target audience, the level of foreign language proficiency, and characteristics of the language environment, require additional investigation.

Due to the importance of technical support in facilitating communication between the university and its target audience, in the present study, the researchers evaluated the number of communication channels (a list of the most frequently used social networks), time, frequency of communication via networks, and technical means of communication.

3 The Study

3.1 Objectives

This study focuses on the communication process performed by students of higher education institutions (HEIs) and prospective students on social networks.

Its subject is the linguistic aspect of communication, particularly the use of English and anglicisms in creating and consuming media content on social networks by non-native English-speaking students at higher education institutions (HEIs).

The primary objective of the present study is to determine the role of the English language in young people's consumption of media content, including education and training, to improve public relations and marketing communications between higher education institutions and their target audience. This endeavour involves determining the nature of the impact of English (a non-native language of contact for the audience under investigation) on the Ukrainian language.

To achieve these objectives, the following scientific issues were examined and addressed:

- The linguistic environment of the target audience, including college and prospective students, with a focus on their native language, their overall language environment, and their proficiency in both foreign and native languages.
- The perception and utilisation of the English language in media content creation by higher education institutions (HEIs) for an audience of non-native English speakers.
- The use among students and prospective students of Ukrainian social networks, which higher education institutions use as modern marketing and public relations channels.
- The potential impact of English, as a prominent and contemporary language, on the Ukrainian language.

3.2 Participants

The target population in the present was students of Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics (State University of Trade and Economics – KNUTE), Kyiv, Ukraine. The medium of instruction at KNUTE is Ukrainian. That is, English is not the native language of communication of the target population in this study, which is the reason behind choosing the target audience.

A sample of 385 respondents participated in the study. 22.7% were males, and 77.3% were females, ranging in age from 15 to 27 years old, with age groups 15-16 (9.4%), 17-18 (58.4), 19-21 (28.1%) and 22-27 (4.1%), with a mean age of 19.31 years old. The data were obtained from October to December 2021 by processing a random sample of KNUTE undergraduate students (from level one to five) enrolled in various programs and courses and their peers and acquaintances aspiring to join the university (prospective students).

The survey was conducted in Kyiv, the capital of Ukraine, based on the location of the State University of Trade and Economics. The target sample of students represented a variety of academic disciplines, including marketing, journalism, commerce and business, IT technology, finance, and accounting. During the survey, students mainly studied online in Kyiv, while others were in different regions of Ukraine. Using

a Google online survey form allowed us to attract respondents from various geographic areas.

As the sample for this study is composed of college students and prospective college students, older age groups, such as university academic or administrative staff and parents, are not represented. However, the collected data was triangulated from various perspectives so that the analysis could provide a comprehensive understanding of the overall situation.

3.3 Methodology

In line with Haque (2017), the methodology used in the present study adopts the following steps:

- A brief exposition of the research design and formulation of the research hypotheses;
- Characteristics of the target audience;
- Descriptions of the instrumentation system (methodology and procedure);
- Analysis procedure;
- Conclusions based on the results of the study and prospects for further research.

The present study represents a theoretical and quantitative analysis of the corpus of data collected, using a questionnaire as a primary research instrument, analysed with Google Analytics tools. In the course of their research, the researchers speculated on the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1

The adoption of anglicisms and the influence of the English language have a significant impact on the Ukrainian language, potentially affecting linguistic purity and native language practices.

Hypothesis 2

The use of social media contributes positively to language communication among Ukrainian youth. It facilitates language exchange and the integration of new linguistic elements.

Hypothesis 3

There is a positive correlation between English and Ukrainian proficiency, social media use, and how young people in Ukraine consume and adapt media content in their native language.

Google Forms, a web-based survey, was used to collect the data. After the survey was designed, respondents were sent an Internet link to access and complete the survey. The resulting facts and figures were subsequently evaluated. The ten qualitative and quantitative survey questions were categorised into three parts, as illustrated below and presented in Tables 1 to 3.

Part 1: Language environment as a basis for introducing and using English in Ukraine:

Question 1: What is the relationship between the characteristics of language milieu and the introduction of anglicism in Ukraine?

Question 2: What is the relationship between the level of English proficiency in Ukraine and the introduction of Anglicism?

Part 2: The use and perception of Anglicisms in the Ukrainian language and media:

Question 3: How are anglicisms perceived in communication and media content in Ukraine?

Question 4: What is the level of English influence on the Ukrainian language?

Question 5: What are the reasons for the diffusion of anglicisms into the Ukrainian language?

Question 6: What is the catalyst for the accelerated diffusion of anglicisms into Ukrainian?

Question 7: Does the use of anglicisms affect an individual's Ukrainian language and speech? And if so, was the effect positive or negative?

Part 3: The target audience's language environment in social networks:

Question 8: Are there any differences between face-to-face- and social-media language communication?

Question 9: What are the reasons for using English in social networks?

Question 10: Does social network communication affect speech? If so, in what way?

The study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, so predominantly multiple-choice quantitative questions were incorporated to ensure the convenience of the survey procedures. Answering several qualitative questions might seem tedious to respondents, but they eventually offered the required data corpus for answering the research questions.

The raw online survey data collected from KUNET's students and prospective students in the three-part context established above were sorted out, cleaned, organised according to the respective survey questions, statistically analysed using Google Analytics tools, interpreted, and presented in tables throughout the discussion.

The methodological choices in this study align closely with its objectives. Focusing on HEI students and prospective students, particularly at KNUTE, enables a targeted exploration of the impact of English on a non-native Ukrainian linguistic environment. The quantitative approach and the large sample size (385 respondents) enhance the robustness of the findings, while the online survey format facilitated participation from different regions, thereby increasing the representativeness of the data.

Structured around three specific hypotheses, the study systematically examines the influence of anglicisms, language exchange on social media, and the correlation

between English and Ukrainian proficiency. This focused, hypothesis-driven framework allowed for clear and thorough analysis, supported by Google Analytics, to capture key linguistic patterns and effectively address the study's research objectives.

3.4. Limitations

The results of the study should be considered with a number of limitations. Firstly, there was a delay of almost four years between data collection and publication, mainly due to unforeseen challenges arising from the ongoing conflict in Ukraine. This disruption necessitated the relocation of one of the authors and resulted in resource constraints, which affected the timeline of the manuscript and may affect the immediacy of its findings.

Furthermore, as the study focuses on a single institution, the Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics, its findings may not fully capture the linguistic behaviours and attitudes of students across other Ukrainian institutions. The reliance on self-reported data is another limitation, as it may introduce subjective biases, particularly in self-assessments of language proficiency and media use. These considerations underscore the need for cautious interpretation and suggest that future research might benefit from a larger sample to provide a more representative view of the influence of English on Ukrainian media and communication.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Language Environment as a Basis for Introducing and Using English in Ukraine

The table summarises the responses of the 385 participants to the survey questions on mother tongue, daily linguistic environment, foreign languages spoken, foreign language proficiency and use of spelling and grammar checking tools in communication. These data provide a basic insight into the role of English in Ukraine's multilingual landscape, showing how factors such as linguistic environment, mother tongue use, foreign language choice and the use of language support tools contribute to the use of English by Ukrainian students.

As shown in the table below, almost half of the respondents (49.9%) considered their daily language environment to be multilingual. This context is likely to support English as a bridge language, adaptable to a variety of interactions and media. In addition, while 28.1% of respondents said their primary language was the same as their daily communication language, 22.0% said they used another language in their daily interactions. This balance between monolingual and multilingual experiences underpins a willingness to integrate English into everyday life, especially in different communication contexts.

Questions	Answer Options	Responses in Percent
Native Language and Language Environment		
Evaluate the language environment you are in on a daily basis.	Multilingual environment	49.9
	My native language is the primary language I use daily.	28.1
	My native language differs from the language I use daily	22.0
Specify your native language	Ukrainian	47.4
	I use both Ukrainian and Russian	39.6
	Russian	12.0
	Other	1.0
Foreign Language Skills		
Specify the foreign languages you speak	English	97.1
	German	13.5
	French	7.6
	Russian	2.1
	Spanish	1.3
	Polish	0.9
Assess your level of foreign language proficiency	A2 and lower	18.8
	B1	36.5
	B2	39.1
	C1	5.6
Do you use spellcheck and automatic grammar correction services?	Yes	64.6
	No	34.1
	It's hard to answer; I don't know what it is	1.3

Table 1: Language Background, Environment, and Foreign Language Proficiency of Respondents

As shown in the table below, almost half of the respondents (49.9%) considered their daily language environment to be multilingual. This context is likely to support English as a bridge language, adaptable to a variety of interactions and media. In

addition, while 28.1% of respondents said their primary language was the same as their daily communication language, 22.0% said they used another language in their daily interactions. This balance between monolingual and multilingual experiences underpins a willingness to integrate English into everyday life, especially in different communication contexts.

In terms of mother tongue, as shown in Table 1, 47.4% of respondents identified Ukrainian as their primary language, 12.0% identified Russian, and 39.6% reported using both Ukrainian and Russian. These figures reveal the complex linguistic environment in which the students operate, with a significant proportion of students balancing bilingual communication. The linguistic diversity of their environment thus supports the integration of English as a *lingua franca* in both formal and informal settings.

The preference for English as a foreign language is clearly strong, with 97.1% of respondents claiming proficiency, as shown in Table 1. German, French, Russian, Spanish and Polish also appeared as secondary choices, but with significantly lower prevalence. When self-assessing their foreign language proficiency, around 75% of respondents rated their skills at the B1-B2 level (36.5% at B1 and 39.1% at B2), suggesting a solid foundation for using English in various domains, including face-to-face communication, social networking and media creation. This level of proficiency is in line with the growing influence of English globally and strengthens its presence in the digital and media sectors in Ukraine.

Another interesting insight from Table 1 is the use of spelling and grammar checking tools, with 64.6% of respondents using these tools to support accurate writing. This practice highlights the importance placed on grammatical accuracy and may indicate that some students are uncertain about their language skills. However, the 34.1% who do not use these tools may reflect a high level of confidence in their language skills or a preference for unaided writing.

In summary, the results presented in Table 1 illustrate that the combination of a multilingual environment, bilingualism in the mother tongue and a high level of English proficiency supports the integration and use of English among Ukrainian students, especially in communication and media-related contexts.

5.2 Use and Perception of Anglicisms in the Ukrainian Language and Media

This section presents and discusses the results in response to the survey questions listed in Table 2 below, focusing on the use of anglicisms, linguistic interference, and reasons for using English.

5.2.1 Anglicisms and the Use of English

As Table 2 below shows, a significant proportion of respondents, 68.5%, said they fully understood the importance of English in media communication and content. At the same time, however, a quarter of the 385 respondents (25%) said that they ignored and did not pay attention to English. In addition, 4.2% of respondents said

they did not understand the importance of anglicisms and the potential discomfort they can cause. This group also expressed difficulty in grasping the broader meaning of English terms, which contributed to their discomfort with the use of anglicisms in communication.

The self-assessment results, as presented in Table 1, show that 58.6% of respondents frequently encountered English as a language of media content, and a significant proportion (40.6%) reported that they only sometimes encountered it. This result reflects the fact that Anglicisms are actively integrated into the Ukrainian language. However, the results of such self-assessments can be subjective and influenced by the communication channels and audience characteristics with which respondents engage:

Questions	Answer Options	Responses in Percent
Perception of Anglicisms		
How do you perceive anglicisms in communication and media content (advertising)?	I fully understand the meaning of English.	68.5
	I ignore them, I do not pay attention to English,	25.5
	I do not understand the importance of anglicisms, or the discomfort they may cause. Difficulty in grasping the broader meanings of English terms.	4.2
	Other (I understand the meaning of anglicisms, but I find their usage are uncomfortable. I understand the meaning, but do not understand the meaning of the use of anglicisms. I very rarely listen to or read advertising)	1.8
How often do you encounter anglicisms in media content (advertising)?	Often	58.6
	Sometimes	40.6
	I do not pay attention to them; I cannot answer this question.	0.8

Reasons for the introduction of Anglicisms		
Why do users, despite having Ukrainian equivalents, continuously replace words with English terms on social networks?	Some Ukrainian equivalents are too complex and do not sound as good as English.	59.1
	Anglicism is an integral part of contemporary speech, often reflecting a more fashionable or trendy style of communication.	53.1
	Using anglicisms helps me to give a specific emotional colour to my communication.	40.9
	Using anglicisms sounds better.	32.0
	The Ukrainian language has not developed equivalents for all technological innovations in time, so it is necessary to adapt English terms.	30.7
	That's what everyone says; I'm trying to be in trend.	3.4
What is the catalyst for the acceleration of Anglicisms?	The popularity of the English language.	84.6
	Thought leaders, celebrities	45.6
	Advertising of famous brands	26.6
	Globalisation English-speaking environments, the desire to stand out, a lack of flexible equivalents, English-speaking environments	1.5
	Viral trends (memes): A cultural or viral idea, image, or trend that spreads rapidly across	0.5

	social media and other platforms	
The Influence of Anglicisms on Speech and the Ukrainian Language		
How does the use of English affect your ability?	It improves my speech.	34.7
	It deteriorates my speech.	9.1
	It does not affect my speech.	3.1
	It is difficult to answer this question.	53.1
	The use of English is a modern process that would happen under any circumstances.	49.3
	It improves the promotion of special terms that are easier to explain in English.	30.7
	Anglicisms cause damage to the Ukrainian language.	12.2
	Anglicisms have a positive influence on the Ukrainian language, improving vocabulary and communication efficiency.	6.5
	At the same time, they improve and worsen the Ukrainian language.	1.2
Other	1.3	

Table 2: Use and Perception of Anglicisms

5.2.2 Reasons for Using English

The following responses were obtained from an analysis of the subjects' responses to the question "Why do users of social networks constantly replace English words for lexical items that have Ukrainian-language equivalents?"

As demonstrated in Table 2, Anglicisms are more meaningful and effective to use (59.1%); English is perceived as a more fashionable or trendy style of communication (53.1%); anglicisms create a distinct emotional flavour in communication (40.9%) and sound better (32.0%). In addition, 30.7% of respondents cited some inertia of the Ukrainian language regarding the use of technological terminology as a reason for the diffusion of English, and most current terms in the digital sphere are ubiquitously present in English.

84.6% of respondents considered the popularity and prevalence of English to be the most influential factors underlying the English diffusion process. In addition, opinion leaders and celebrities (45.6%), as well as advertising by well-known brands (26.6%), have a significant influence on this diffusion into the Ukrainian language and media content (Table 2 above).

5.2.3 The Influence of English on Facilitating Communication and the Ukrainian Language

In particular, the evaluation of the impact of English in facilitating communication is somewhat abstract and subjective. As a result, a substantial proportion of respondents (53.1%) were unable to assess this effect on their own speech. However, 34.7% indicated a positive influence, 9.1% a negative influence, and 3.1% no influence, at all.

Among the target audience, both positive (6.5%) and negative (12.2%) effects of the English language on the Ukrainian language were identified. 1.2% of respondents indicated the existence of both positive and negative effects. In conclusion, almost half of the respondents (49.3%) considered the use of English as a modern process, regardless of the reasons for its spread. 30.7% of respondents observed a better understanding and promotion of easier to explain technical terms in English.

5.3 The target Audience's Language Environment on Social Media

This subsection discusses and presents the results obtained concerning anglicisms and their use in social media and Internet communication, as shown in Table 3 below.

5.3.1 The Use of Social Media

From the sample of 385 matriculated and prospective students, we found that all students used at least one social media site. Instagram (94.5%), Telegram (98.7%), YouTube (89.8%), Facebook (27.3%), and Twitter (13.8%) were among the sites used by respondents as media consumers and for academic purposes. In addition, TikTok had a user base of 3.5% of respondents, while WhatsApp, Viber, Snapchat, and LinkedIn had a user base of 0.6%.

The respondents widely use social media: 71.4 % have been active on social media for more than five years, 23.4% for three to five years, 4.7% for one to three years, and 0.5% for less than one year (Table 3 below).

Respondents reported the following daily social media usage: 52.9% are “always ready for communication”, 19.5% devote three to five hours per day, 21.1% devote one to two hours, and 6.5% devote less than one hour. Unsurprisingly, none of the respondents reported zero hours spent on social networks. Consequently, the consumption levels for around-the-clock communication are the highest. The number of social media used by the respondents is at least three (Telegram, Instagram, YouTube), as shown in Table 3.

All respondents (100%) reported using a social media website on a laptop, which increased the approachability and flexibility of communication. However, 69.5% utilised mobile devices, and only 6.3% used tablets.

5.3.2 Language of Communication and Social Media

According to the results, 69.5% of respondents identified Russian as the dominant language of communication on social networks, Ukrainian (25.0%), and English (2.3%), as only 0.3% of respondents mostly speak it. In addition, about 3.0% of respondents used several languages simultaneously:

Questions	Answer Options	Responses in Percent
Profile of Using Social Networks		
What social networks do you use?	Telegram	98.7
	Instagram	94.5
	YouTube	89.8
	Facebook	27.3
	Twitter	13.8
	TikTok	3.5
	WhatsApp	0.6
	Viber	0.6
	Snapchat	0.6
	LinkedIn	0.5
What is the duration of your active use of social networks?	More than five years	71.4
	3-5 years	23.4
	1-3 years	4.7
	Less than one year	0.5
What is the duration of your daily communication on social networks?	I am always ready to communicate	52.9
	3-5 hours	19.5
	1-2 hours	21.1
	Less than 1 hour	6.5
Name the devices you use to communicate on social networks	Laptop	69.5
	Smartphone	100.0
	Tablet	6.3

Language of Communication and Social Networks		
Specify your dominant language of communication (on social networks)	Ukrainian	25.0
	Russian	69.5
	English	2.3
	I use several languages at the same time	3.2
Do you use English when communicating online? Why?	It is easier to name some concepts in this way	66.1
	Yes, because that's what my friends say	13.0
	This is part of my job; for the development of speech and writing	12.3
	Fashionable and part of my style	8.3
	No, I do not use English, at all	3.8
	I use it by accident because I mostly speak English	0.3
How often do you use English when communicating on social networks?	Sometimes	58.9
	Often	35.2
	I do not use it / I almost do not use it.	0.3
Do you think that communication on social networks affects your speech? In what way?	Examples of words are city, trash, wow	5.6
	It improves my speech.	29.7
	It deteriorates my speech.	12.0
	It is difficult to answer.	54.4
	Does not affect my speech.	1.2
	Other	2.7

Table 3: The Language of the Target Audience in Social Networks

The fact that Ukraine is not an English-speaking country explains the low percentage of respondents who use English as a language of communication on social networks. Here, English is used mainly for international cooperation by government agencies. According to students' self-assessment results, however, there is a relatively significant level of English language proficiency among respondents (B1 - 36.5%) and B2 - 39.1%, as shown in Table 1).

The outcome of student's responses regarding the use of Russian is indicative. 69.5% of respondents use it when communicating on social networks. The use of the term reflects the freedom to choose the language of communication, as media coverage of Russia's military aggression against Ukraine and allegations of oppression of the Russian-speaking population has intensified. It has to be remembered

that the present study was conducted in November-December 2021, shortly before the Russian military aggression against Ukraine in February 2022.

Most respondents (66.1%) attributed using English for social network communication to the ease of identifying concepts in this language. 13.0% related it to its function as a means of communication with their peers, while 8.3% related it to its status as being in fashion. Approximately 3.8% of respondents did not speak English in the first place.

The most significant proportion of respondents (58.9%) reported that they "sometimes" used English, and 35.2% said they often used it. Nevertheless, 0.3% of respondents did not use English or used it very little (Table 3).

As shown in Table 3, 29.7% of respondents thought that communication on social networks improved their language and 12.0% thought that it made their language worse. At the same time, 45.4% found it difficult to make a connection and only 1.2% reported no effect. The small proportion of 1.2% could be attributed to respondents who maintained a strong separation between their online communication and everyday speech, or those who had not experienced any noticeable changes in their language as a result of social media.

5 Conclusions

In the past few decades, social media have become an integral part of human life. This process intensified considerably during the Covid-19 pandemic. Different target groups consume media content depending on their needs and interests. Therefore, the content, form of presentation, and language of media content are becoming increasingly essential. The language of the information message is one of the factors that determines the effectiveness of communication.

This study has examined KNUTE matriculated and prospective students' use of English as a non-native language in communicating and consuming media content, as well as their command of foreign languages, their language proficiency, and their perceptions to identify the relationship between their English proficiency and the use of anglicism in the Ukrainian language during their communication processes and consumption of social media content.

The study concludes with a high diffusion rate of English as a foreign language into the subjects' communication content and their significantly increased proficiency levels, averaging between B1 and B2 among 75% of the target audiences, which creates favourable conditions for the use of English in communication and the creation of media content for Ukrainian higher education institutions. At the top of the list was the prominence and prevalence of the English language (84.5% of respondents), the influence of opinion leaders and personalities (45.6%) and, finally, advertising by well-known brands (26.6%). In addition, Telegram (98.7%), Instagram (94.5%), YouTube (89.8%), Facebook (27.3%), and Twitter (13%) were identified as the most prominent social networks employed by respondents for communication.

The majority of respondents (66.1%) attributed their use of anglicism to the simplicity of concept identification in English, 13% to English being the communication language of their peers, and 8.2% to English being fashionable and part of their lifestyle. Only 3.8% of respondents indicated never using English.

These conclusions demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating English as a foreign language into students' personal communication, the creation of media content and higher education institutions' communication with students and applicants via social networks.

The most important aspect of this study is its usefulness to higher education institutions as leading creators of media content. (e.g. in advertising on the education market), to academics in their quest to provide students with effective teaching content and guidance to develop their language skills. Undoubtedly, this enlightened management will benefit them as consumers and users of social media in their learning, studying, working and communicating.

The findings of this study underscore the increasing prevalence of English in the communication practices of Ukrainian students, particularly in relation to social media consumption. The high level of English proficiency observed among participants, with a significant proportion in the B1-B2 range, suggests a substantial opportunity for HEIs to integrate English more thoroughly into their academic provision. Institutions should consider the strategic integration of English-language content in both curriculum design and digital resources, ensuring that the language of instruction and communication is appropriate to students' proficiency levels and media consumption habits.

Furthermore, the widespread use of anglicisms in students' everyday communication, driven by their perceived ease of concept identification and the influence of peer groups, suggests that English terms are becoming an integral part of students' lexicon. This trend presents both an opportunity and a challenge for higher education institutions, particularly in terms of maintaining linguistic standards while embracing the pragmatic use of anglicisms. Educational content that incorporates both English and Ukrainian terms should be considered, balancing linguistic authenticity with the evolving linguistic landscape of students.

The dominance of social media platforms such as Telegram, Instagram and YouTube in students' communication practices highlights the importance of these channels for effective engagement. Higher education institutions should recognise the role of digital media in students' academic lives and develop targeted strategies to use these platforms to promote academic content and foster language development. Given the influence of opinion leaders and brand advertising, universities need to keep abreast of global media trends and students' changing language practices in order to remain relevant in their communication strategies.

Ultimately, these findings suggest that higher education institutions need to adopt a more nuanced approach to language policy and media engagement, ensuring that their communication strategies reflect the linguistic and cultural realities of a globalised, digitally connected student body. By aligning institutional content with students' language practices, universities can enhance both academic com-

munication and student engagement, fostering a more effective learning environment.

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